

COLOUR IN RELATION TO THE CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION OF THE METALLIC DERIVATIVES OF *iso*NITROSOMALONYLGUANIDINE

BY ROSHAN LAL HANDA AND SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT

Metallic derivatives of *isonitrosomalonylguanidine* have been prepared by the interaction of the potassium salt with various other metallic salts in aqueous solution. All the metallic derivatives prepared are brightly coloured substances having shades different from one another. Chemical analyses point to the existence of co-ordination compounds amongst these metallic derivatives.

*iso*Nitrosomalonylurea or violuric acid, which forms interesting pink coloured salts with organic and inorganic bases and dissolves in water to a pale pink solution, has been the subject of intensive study by Ghatak and Dutt (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 665) who from the absorption spectra of these compounds have come to the conclusion that although the structure of violuric acid itself is the oximino-ketonic form (I), yet in the process of salt formation the nitroso-enolic structure (II) is produced by the migration of a hydrogen atom.

A similar behaviour was observed by Lal and Dutt (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1937, 3, 377) in the case of thiovioluric acid in which the oxygen atom in violuric acid marked with an asterisk had been replaced by a sulphur atom. This replacement was found to produce intensification in the colour of the salt to violet instead of pink, due to increased load in juxtaposition to the chromophore.

*iso*Nitrosomalonylguanidine (III)

which is structurally very closely related to violuric and thiovioluric acid has been found to yield intensely coloured salt with organic and inorganic bases, the organic salts having been already prepared and described by Dass and Dutt (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9, 93). The inorganic salts of this interesting compound form the subject of the present investigation. While the organic salts have been found to exhibit mainly violet colour in aqueous solution, the inorganic salts have a wide range of colour from yellow and pink to dark blue and green. From the point of view of analogy of violuric and thiovioluric acids, the metallic salts of *isonitrosomalonylguanidine* should correspond to the nitroso-enolic structure of this substance which may have two alternative forms (IV, V):

(IV)

(V)

Theoretical considerations show that in either of these forms the metallic salts of isonitrosomalonylguanidine are probably of the nature of interally complex compounds. The acid molecule in its nitroso-enolic form contains one replaceable hydrogen atom which can be replaced by the metal atom during salt formation. The possibility of inner complex salt formation arises whenever acidic and donor functions (such as amino, carbonyl, etc. groups) are suitably placed in the same molecule, i.e., in 1:4 or 1:5 positions to one another. The molecule of isonitrosomalonylguanidine contains a nitrogen atom in 1:4 position to the replaceable hydrogen atom and has got one lone pair of electrons. By virtue of this lone pair of electrons, the nitrogen atom can act as a donor and form a co-ordinate link with the metal atom, for which the electrons are supplied by the nitrogen atom. The co-ordinating power of the nitrogen atom is well known in the complex aminines of cobalt and other metals and a large number of other co-ordination compounds. That chelation can take place readily when the two atoms concerned in chelation are in 1:4 position is also a well known fact. Another peculiar feature about these compounds is that in some cases the tendency of the metal atom to acquire the most stable co-ordination number is over-ridden by the valency requirements of the metal atom concerned. In view of the fact that the molecule of isonitrosomalonylguanidine contains a replaceable hydrogen atom, the number of molecules of the acid which will react with one atom of the metal will be equal to the valency of the metal. The acid molecule as a whole acts as a bidentate chelate radical and thus the co-ordination number of the metal atom will be equal to twice its valency. This sort of behaviour is exemplified by other co-ordination compounds whose structures are well known, e.g., the cobalt salt of ethyl tetramethylpyrromethane-4:4'-dicarboxylate (VI) (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 368) and dimethylglyoxime complex of nickel (VII).

(VI)

(VII)

That the metallic derivatives of isonitrosomalonylguanidine are of the nature of inner complexes is further supported by the fact that the salts are very stable. Moreover, their insolubility in water and solubility in organic solvents also support this view. The salts do not possess such high melting points as true salts, which is also in favour of the suggestion that they are of the nature of co-ordination compounds. The salts of bi- and tri-valent metals may thus be given the following general formula where M is the metal atom (VIII).

Alternatively they may also be formulated as shown below (IX) whereby a six-membered ring may be formed:

EXPERIMENTAL

*iso*Nitrosomalonylguanidine was prepared according to the method given by Dass and Dutt (*loc. cit.*). The potassium salt of the compound was prepared in the following way: *iso*Nitrosomalonylguanidine (15.6 g.) was ground up into a thick cream with water (50 c.c.) and the whole converted into an almost clear, crimson solution by the addition of a 20% aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide (30 c.c.). After filtering, the solution was treated with an excess of rectified spirit (95%, 350 c.c.), when the potassium salt was gradually deposited in the form of glistening violet needles. After keeping in the refrigerator overnight, the product was filtered off, washed with cold rectified spirit (150 c.c.) and ether (50 c.c.) and dried in the air-oven at 70°. Yield of the potassium salt corresponded to nearly 95% of the theoretical (18.6 g.).

For the preparation of the metallic derivatives, the aqueous or aqueous-alcoholic solution of the salt of the metal (the chloride or the nitrate, whichever was more soluble) was gradually added to a 10% aqueous solution of the potassium salt of *isonitrosomalonylguanidine*, until the former was in slight excess. The metallic derivative was immediately precipitated in fine crystalline form which very often took the shape of glistening prismatic needles. This was filtered off, washed with aqueous alcohol and then with pure alcohol and dried. The yields of the salts in most cases were practically quantitative and in no case less than 90% of the theoretical calculated on the basis of the potassium salt of *isonitrosomalonylguanidine* employed. In a few cases the salts were soluble in some organic solvents (chiefly acetone) and could be recrystallised from them. But in many cases this could not be done as they were found to be insoluble in

all organic solvents. As prepared, however, the salts were found to be quite pure and yielded fairly good analytical data. It was noted that all the metallic derivatives of isonitrosomalonylguanidine described in this paper have different colours. They all melt with decomposition at comparatively low temperatures. For the sake of abbreviation, the experimental details have been summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour.	Decomp point.	Solvent from which crystallised.	Metal		Nitrogen	
				found.	calc.	found.	calc.
K	Deep violet	192°	Hot water ; purple colour in soln.	19.95%	20.1%	28.767%	28.87%
Li	Deep pink	205°	Acetone ; pink colour in soln.	4.268	4.292	33.79	34.58
Ca	Pinkish yellow	218°	Could not be obtained in soln.	28.16	27.949	26.53	26.05
Ba	Red	235°	„	46.67	46.98	16.45	16.25
Mg	Pale yellow	226°	„	19.15	19.05	29.23	26.82
Zn	Dirty white	260°	„	39.17	38.75	22.64	22.12
Cd	Yellowish white	235°	„	26.79	26.62	26.41	26.52
Hg	Yellowish brown	254°	„	66.1	66.0	11.95	12.28
Al	Grey	210°	„	5.539	5.488	33.83	34.14
Pb	White	196°	„	40.5	40.06	21.24	21.67
Bi	Light blue	206°	Acetone ; light purple colour in soln.	31.59	31.01	24.59	24.95
Mn	Deep chocolate	258°	Could not be obtained in soln.	34.53	34.71	23.81	23.59
Co	Snuff-coloured	245°	„	35.6	36.39	22.92	23.04
Ni	Dark green	225°	„	36.47	36.43	22.98	23.04
Ferrous	Deep blue	225°	„	35.3	35.081	23.57	23.49
Ferric	Bluish green	220°	„	26.35	26.53	25.96	26.54
Cu	Dark green	214°	„	50.16	50.63	17.44	17.83
U	Deep yellow	191°	„	71.6	69.72	10.54	10.93
Ce	Light brown	Does not decompose up to 300°	„	47.82	48.58	18.48	18.99
Th	Dirty brown	220°	„	50.42	49.96	17.92	18.08